

Combining Student-Led Lab Activities with Computational Practices to Promote Sensemaking in Financial Mathematics

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Creating an engaging enquiry-based teaching environment in computational science modules is fundamental in the development of a deep understanding of the underlying principles, relations, and core concepts in the related subject. In this contribution we describe how we have implemented computational lab practices in a Computational Finance undergraduate module to foster students' computational thinking and overall learning. In particular, we discuss the use of computation jointly with groups activities as central elements to facilitate sensemaking in Financial Mathematics and we show how the modern definition of "inclusive computation" has been embedded harmonically in the design of tailored student-led lab practices.

Introduction

In the last few years, the need for well-prepared STEM graduates, equipped with data analysis and computational modelling skills, has increased in both modern academia and industry. There has been increased attention on computation in mathematical subjects (Lockwood et al., 2019), and consequently traditional undergraduate education has been adapted in different ways. One strategy has been to make use of tailored computational and problem-solving activities where students must work in groups to solve complex problems in realistic STEM contexts (Irving et al., 2017). In this setting, Computational Finance is a relatively new and highly interdisciplinary subject, fundamental to cover high-level roles in the financial sector and to master Financial Mathematics as well. Whilst some researchers refer to a body of literature in Finance Education (Diamond & Smith, 2011; Hoadley et al., 2015, 2016) only a limited portion of these specifically investigate the Computational Finance curriculum; thus, the area is under-researched. The focus of this paper is to show how we have implemented specific computational lab practices in ACM30070, Computational Finance, a core module in stage 3 of the BSc in Financial Mathematics, School of Mathematics and Statistics, UCD. We describe how the modern definition of "inclusive computation" (Caballero & Hjorth-Jensen, 2018) has been embedded within a student-led educational activities and how specific lab practices have been accordingly designed. In particular, we show how those practices contribute reciprocally to use computational thinking to enrich the mastery of financial mathematics and the theory of financial mathematics to enrich students' computational thinking.

Context and Learning Goals

The purpose of ACM30070 is to provide a practitioner-oriented education in implementing financial models and to embed computational thinking in mathematical and financial contexts, with the aim of bringing current educational efforts in line with the increasing demand for problem-solving and quantitative skills in the industry. The module is core for stage 3 students attending the BSc in Financial Mathematics (FM), and it is optional

for stage 3 students attending the BSc in Applied and Computational Mathematics (ACM). In total, 50 students attend the module, with 35 FM and 15 ACM. In stage 1 and 2 both FM and ACM students attend modules on Pure and Applied Mathematics, Statistics and Finance (FM students only), but they do not have any prior exposure to computational modelling of real-world financial problems. They also attend an introductory coding module in Python. To set up the learning goals, a series of discussions with STEM education researchers and industry professionals has been ongoing since 2016. Starting from the outcomes of those conversations and referring to the principles of backward course design (Wiggins & McTighe, 2005), we agreed that upon successful completion of the module, students will be able to: apply financial mathematical theory and quantitative methodologies to real-world situations; understand industry practices; identify salient features of a financial system that can be translated into a model; judge the suitability of a model, critically understanding its limitations; write computer code to solve common problems in the financial sector; collect, create, manipulate and analyse financial datasets; understand basic numerical methods and use them to solve problems; synthesize and communicate outcomes of a scientific computing problem.

To design the overall course structure, we referred to the Seven Research-Based Principles for Smart Teaching described in Ambrose et al. (2010). Those principles focus on how learning begins with empirical evidence; for this reason, they can be easily applied in classes where students have a modest background in a subject, which is the case for students enrolling in ACM30070. A comprehensive description of the module design process can be found in Perrotta (2021). Keeping in mind the aforementioned learning outcomes and the fact that “engagement and motivations strongly influence what students learn” (Ambrose et al., 2010), one of the main drivers in any design component was making the study of computational finance as authentic and engaging as possible through practices set in a real-world financial context. The choice of student-led lab practices aims also to foster FM students’ motivation, achievement, persistence and retention (Good et al., 2012; Irving et al., 2017). In particular, Funkhouser et al. (2018) have shown that the laboratory is the ideal place for students to feel part of an academic community, since they have the opportunity to engage in authentic practices and build knowledge through collaboration with peers.

In this paper we focus on a detailed description of the lab activities in ACM30070, Spring 2021 offering, and we show how the above considerations and the modern definition of “inclusive computation” have been essential to build group practices, to develop computational thinking and to foster sensemaking in financial mathematics.

Theoretical Background

In this section we offer an initial working definition of computing and its relationship to computational thinking and modelling. Then, we introduce the modern definition of “inclusive computation”. Finally, we provide the general definition of sensemaking in science education and list the steps of sensemaking process.

Computing and Computational Thinking

The definition of *computing* is prone to several interpretations as it includes many different activities. The K-12 Computer Science Framework presents computing as features of

computer literacy, education technology, digital citizenship, IT and computer science (K-12 Computer Science Framework, 2016, p.13-14). Weintrop et al. (2016) develop a Computational Practice Taxonomy, focusing on the application of computational thinking to mathematics and science (p.128). In our study we referred to the following definition of computation in mathematics: “the practice of using tools to perform mathematical calculations or to develop or implement algorithms in order to accomplish a mathematical goal” (Lockwood et al. 2019, p.3). By calculations, we include both numerical and symbolic ones, such as simplifying algebraic expressions, generating numerical structures with particular characteristics, or numerically estimating error. The tools used in calculation could range from pen and paper to a particular programming language depending on the complexity of the problem at hand. From an algorithmic perspective, computing involves developing, using, or implementing a logical sequence of steps known as an algorithm. Using computation in financial mathematics has several potential benefits: students can engage in the modelling process to make complex problems manageable, and they can use computation to explore the applicability and utility of underlying financial principles. Strictly connected to computation is the definition of computational thinking and computational modelling. The notion of computational thinking has historical roots that stretch back for decades (see Tedre and Denning (2016) for a historical account). Wing (2006), modernized the term describing it as “taking an approach to solving problems, designing systems and understanding human behaviour that draws on concepts fundamental to computer science” (p. 33). In subsequent years other researchers have refined the definition (e.g., Aho, 2012). In a 2014 blog post, Wing articulated the definition we currently adopt: “Computational thinking is the thought processes involved in formulating a problem and expressing its solution(s) in such a way that a computer - human or machine - can effectively carry out” (Wing, 2014).

Inclusive Computation

Starting from the above definitions of computing and computational thinking, we referred to the “inclusive computation” framework introduced by Caballero & Hjorth-Jensen (2018). In this framework, computation practices are not restricted to writing programme statements from scratch, learn a coding language syntax and debugging a code. In fact, the “*inclusive computation*” definition includes a wide range of high-level coding activities like: having students working on their own or in groups with simulations and/or algorithms to understand the main characteristics of a mathematical/physical/financial model; giving students pieces of code to complete or modify on their own or in groups in order to adapt them to a different problem; critically inspecting and judging computational inputs and outputs; advising students on open-ended group projects where they write code from scratch.

Inclusive computational practices have been heavily used to design physics undergraduates’ modules in Michigan State University and Georgia Tech, USA (e.g., Caballero et al., 2012; Caballero & Hjorth-Jensen, 2018). They have included computation and computational thinking as a central element, and not simply as a tool in the design process. We have adapted such definition to a financial mathematics context, proposing lab activities pertinent to students’ future professions (Barrett & Moore, 2011; Schmidt et al. 2009). Students are constrained by the programming language to certain syntactic structures

and must learn to contextualize problems in a way that produces a precise representation of the financial model. They learn how to use computation, computational thinking and financial mathematics, in harmony, to solve a real-world financial problem and to identify important features of a financial system that can be translated into a model. Finally, students understand how to judge the suitability of a model and critically grasp its limitations. Below, we include a detailed case study to show how inclusive computation has been implemented in practice.

Sensemaking in Science Education

The problem of investigating how students can “make sense” of science became relevant in recent years. However, even if many researchers agree on an intuitive definition of *sensemaking*, the related literature is fragmented. Odden & Russ (2017) propose the following definition, that we adopt as theoretical framework: “sensemaking is a dynamic process of building or revising an explanation in order to “figure something out”—to ascertain the mechanism underlying a phenomenon in order to resolve a gap or inconsistency in one's understanding.” (p.3). We refer to this definition because it unifies the three primary approaches describing sensemaking: sensemaking as an epistemological frame, as a cognitive process and as a discourse practice. In summary, the process of sensemaking involves (a) realising that there is a gap or contradiction in one's knowledge, (b) iteratively proposing ideas and attempting to connect them to prior knowledge or other ideas, and (c) evaluating that these ideas are consistent and do not lead to additional contradictions. In this paper, we show how inclusive computational practices (defined above) may provide opportunities for sensemaking in computational finance in a lab setting.

Toward Lab Practices

Lab activities in ACM30070 are intended to build a teaching environment in which students can develop a deeper and more robust knowledge in FM. Sensemaking will grow as students are actively made accountable in the construction of their knowledge. The weekly schedule, the technology and logistics chosen, and the staff selection have strongly contributed in supporting these objectives and in preparing students to be independent learners. In terms of weekly schedule, students attend 4 slots of 50 minutes each per week, divided into two lectures, one tutorial, and one lab scheduled at the end of the week. To pre-activate learning and individual reflections, pre-class materials are uploaded on the course management system. Those materials typically include slides, notes, short videos as well as proper formative assignments like guided programming activities and/or working questions. The lectures are devoted to the financial modelling part, while tutorials are intended for computational practices and problem-solving activities. Lectures and tutorials are aimed to provide students with suitable skills and knowledge to make them as independent as possible in performing the weekly lab activities, given that they are fully student-led. In terms of technology and logistics, since “students' motivation determines, directs, and sustains what they do to learn” (Ambrose et al. 2010), we chose specific digital technologies and programming languages that are meaningful from an educational perspective and used in the financial industry. Students attending ACM30070 learn VBA for Excel, Python and Fincad (FAS). FAS is a financial software widely used in financial firms. It is very helpful for learning, since it is intuitive to use, and each workbook is equipped with extensive

documentation on both the theory and computational side. VBA for Excel and Fincad are also frequently used to create complex financial spreadsheet models. Python programming is easy to learn, the code is compact and in general highly readable, as its syntax is close to that of mathematics. Python programs are developed in Spyder notebooks, allowing easy access to not only raw code but also the results of its execution throughout, plots and powerful data analysis. Beyond the technology, the “physical” classroom space has been crucial to support the student-led aspect. Before March 2020, all activities took place in Active Learning rooms, equipped with round tables and movable whiteboards. To adapt this class format to off-campus teaching, the classes have been live-streamed on Zoom in Spring 2021. The round tables and class discussions have been substituted with the “breakout rooms” and “poll” features in Zoom and practices have been redesigned to be delivery-mode independent.

Finally, problem-based learning environments and student-led activities require the facilitation of experts to ensure that students have a productive and engaging experience. As a result, we took great care in the selection of the tutor (T) and teaching assistant (TA). The current T attended the module in 2018-19 as a FM student, and was the TA in 2019-20. The TA attended the module in 2019-20. Both were among the best performing students in their year. In preparation for their roles, they were provided with the aforementioned literature on problem-based learning, inclusive computation and sensemaking. They also received a one-day training on module contents, module schedule, assessment components and how to guide and scaffold student learning before the start of term. Finally, 20-minute briefing and debriefing meetings with the lecturer (L) have been organized on a weekly basis for each lab during the term. Additionally, both the T and TA received funding to further develop learning materials for the module. Using their perspectives as students, they heavily tailored content to facilitate student-led discussions and attend to students’ needs.

Lab Practices

As mentioned above, weekly lab activities are fully student-led and involve the participation of the L, the T and the TA as facilitators. The same lab structure is proposed each week, but it is applied to different kinds of practices. There is no pre-class assignment; all activities are entirely covered in the lab. In preparation for the specific day activity, students are required to review the contents of the weekly lectures and tutorial. During the first part of the lab, students work in groups on modelling, pseudocoding, data analysis and other related activities (see example below). To foster the student-led aspect of the labs and peers’ collaboration, the L and the T observe the groups’ discussions and, only if needed, will intervene to: give some hints on implementing the day’s lab, guide students’ brainstorming or pose relevant questions to address critical thinking. In the second part, each group chooses a representative to present the group outcomes to the whole class. The L and T guide groups in presenting their results and encourage dialogue between groups in order to come to a conclusion. The TA acts as a moderator in groups dynamics, answering easier questions and takes field notes during the whole lab.

The selection of the groups has been central to foster engagement and peer-learning. Groups were constructed by the L and stayed the same for the whole term. Students are grouped according to their ability, based on historical academic performance to date (the L

has access to all past grades of any student); gender and possible minorities balance have also been taken into account. There are two concepts that are central to support motivation: the *subjective value of a goal* and the *expectancies*, or expectations for successful attainment of that goal (Ambrose et al., 2010). To positively set students' expectation to contribute to the group success, groups member had similar annual GPA to date and they were made aware of that. This way, they were all *expected to be able to contribute in the same way* within their group. Neither leader-follower dynamics nor pedagogical problems were observed during the group' activities. Both individual and group formative feedbacks have been provided weekly. Annotated slides, question solutions and full working codes are provided after each class/lab to give students the opportunity to self-reflect on the activities done. Finally, after each lab, students are invited to fill out a Google Form survey to critically reflect on the activities.

The following case study is introduced by way of example; it shows how topics have been presented in a scaffolded manner to lead students to connect prior and new knowledge, and to apply what they have already learned to new related contexts. In particular, this case study exemplifies how inclusive computational practices have been designed and integrated for sensemaking, and how student-led practices and group activities have been implemented.

The Implied Volatility Case Study

This case study has been developed to offset the difficulties encountered by the students in approaching the concept of implied volatility of a European Vanilla Option. Usually, students learn the definition of implied volatility and run a code to compute it, but they do not understand the mathematical assumptions and relation linking implied volatility and option price. This practice consists of three exercises, of increasing levels of difficulty. It has been designed following the steps of the sensemaking process and using some of the inclusive computational practices described above. The implied volatility model has been developed during the lectures. Since there is a non-linear relation between option price and volatility, a root-finder algorithm is needed for its calculation and the related code has been presented during the tutorial. Before attending the current lab, students are required to review those materials. The lab opens with the T doing a quick walk-through of the tutorial code, followed by the presentation of the first exercise, where students have to figure out why the code breaks down for a given set of input data (step 1 sensemaking). The key faulty element in this first exercise is not a syntax or coding error, but an incoherence between the provided dataset and the model assumptions. To enhance the student-led aspect of the practice, students do not receive any initial hint from the L or the T, instead they have been equipped with a debugging worksheet and a few questions to drive them in collaboration. Thanks to discussions between group members, facilitated at a later time by the L and the T, they learn how to critically inspect and judge computational inputs and outputs and how to integrate the mathematical and computational modelling (step 2 sensemaking). As a second exercise, they are provided with another (working) set of input data and they are required to do a sensitive analysis (step 3 sensemaking). As a third exercise, assigned as a homework, they are required to individually adapt the model, modify the code and perform a sensitive analysis for a different option type. Finally, they are required to bring their solution at the next lab to discuss the individual outcomes in each group and propose a unique class solution.

Conclusions

The over-arching purpose of the lab practices described in this paper is to help students to develop a robust knowledge allowing them to understand and/or create financial models, translate them into code and both quantitatively and qualitatively compare these models with real-world data. The use of an inclusive definition of computation jointly with suitable technology have been central to contribute to sensemaking. In this framework, computation is not simply a skill to learn but it represents one of the constitutive pillars to master financial mathematics within an enquiry-based and student-centred learning environment. In this paper we have described the design process, the theoretical framework and the implementation plan of ACM30070 lab activities, aimed to harmonize student-led practices with inclusive computational practices to promote sensemaking in financial mathematics. We have also explained how groups' activities coupled with moderators' interaction allowed for a free-flowing student-led experience. A case study has been presented as an example. The labs received very positive feedback from students. Two students quoted:

“I think that the labs that require us to design some code in real-world scenarios help me to understand the computational part of the course best. It's one thing to read the other code and implement it but the opportunity to write your own forces you to understand the deeper intricacies in the code and you become more aware of the parts that you do and do not understand, which you can then fix.”

“The group work was very helpful today. It helped us understand the different thought processes that go into creating a specific macro and what the correct outcomes are. It's important to see that just because you did something differently to someone else it does not mean that you are incorrect. There are similar advantage and disadvantage to the method that you or the person whose code you are comparing against have with your respective code. I liked working alongside others.”

Given the importance of computation in modern science and the lack of literature referring to computational finance, our next step is to contribute to educational research. In particular, we want to investigate and measure to what extent the enquiry-based and student-led practices, as well as the “inclusive” computational practices proposed are successful in effectively facilitating sensemaking in FM. In-class data collection for this research study ran in ACM30070 Spring 2021 offering. We collected quantitative and qualitative data including: weekly lab and tutorial attendance, continuous assessment grades, final grades, group project numerical outputs as quantitative data, labs field notes, weekly Google Form, a final Google Form and group project diaries, as qualitative data. Data analysis will start in July 2021 with outputs expected for a future work.

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